

Hydrogen-Deuterium Exchange Coupled to Mass

Spectrometry-based analysis of phytochrome photoreceptors

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Structural analysis of phytochrome photoreceptors using Hydrogen-Deuterium Exchange Coupled to Mass Spectrometry

Abstract

Red light sensing phytochromes typically have at least two functionally distinct conformations, a red absorbing Pr state and a far-red absorbing Pfr state. Understanding the structural differences between these functional states is key to appreciating aspects of light signal integration at the molecular level. Through potentially different interactions with downstream effectors, they can also lay the foundation for gaining better insights at an organismal level.

The multi-domain architecture of many full-length phytochromes makes them challenging targets for detailed structural analysis using classical X-ray crystallography or nuclear magnetic resonance approaches. While recent advances in cryo-electron microscopy offer a promising alternative, the inherently dynamic nature of photoreceptors can also be challenging for single-particle analysis. In this chapter, we describe an alternative approach for the structural analysis of phytochromes, hydrogen deuterium exchange coupled to mass spectrometry (HDX-MS). This in-solution technique permits investigation of the conformational dynamics of proteins via the readout of their secondary structure stability. The ease of using different light regimes to enrich either Pr or Pfr states in solution is illustrated using the model bacteriophytochrome system from *Deinococcus radiodurans*. However, HDX-MS also offers the possibility of extracting the corresponding structural information from ensembles with partial Pr or Pfr states.

Key words

HDX-MS, Conformational dynamics, Light activation, Signal integration, Bacteriophytochrome, BphP

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HDX-MS analysis of phytochromes

1 Introduction

Phytochromes typically function as sensors of red or far-red light and integrate this information of ambient light conditions into downstream signalling cascades to regulate important cellular functions in cyanobacteria, bacteria, fungi and plants **(1)**. In order to perform their function, they need to exist in at least two functionally different states. For bacterial, fungal, and plant phytochromes, these two conformations are typically referred to as the Pr and Pfr states, absorbing in red and far-red, respectively. Characteristics of these two meta-stable ground state conformations are structural differences in the surrounding of the light-sensing bilin cofactors **(1)**, however, the conformational dynamics of the bilin environments and associated structural and functional elements also play an important role in the signal integration mechanism **(2–5)**.

Here, we describe a method that allows the characterisation of in-solution conformational dynamics of full-length phytochromes in particular and photoreceptors in general that can easily be extended to include complexes with functionally relevant ligands and/or target effector proteins. Since the strength of the hydrogen bonds between the peptide amide hydrogens and carbonyl oxygens in alpha helices and beta sheets correlates with secondary structure stability, the rate of hydrogen-deuterium exchange can be employed as a proxy for the conformational dynamics of proteins **(6, 7)**. Due to the inherent mass difference between hydrogen and deuterium, mass spectrometry offers a straightforward readout of the deuterium exchange kinetics. Especially upon including protease digestion in the workup routine, the conformational dynamics of specific structural elements can be assigned using hydrogen-deuterium exchange coupled to mass spectrometry (HDX-MS). More importantly, however, the comparison of light-responsive systems in their dark-adapted states with the corresponding light-activated or photostationary states (PSSs) allows the identification of structural elements involved in light signal integration and communication to downstream functional regions. The versatility of performing these experiments also in the presence of specific ligands or substrates, as well as variants of the protein of interest, provides access to structural information of different functionally relevant states that is otherwise difficult to obtain. To illustrate the workflow, we show

representative results for a paradigm bacterial model system, BphP from *Deinococcus radiodurans* (*DrBphP*) (**8, 9**), in its dark-adapted and PSS conformation.

2 Materials

Prepare all solutions using ultrapure water and chemicals of LC-MS grade. The solutions must be prepared and pH/pD adjusted at the specified temperatures.

2.1 Solutions and buffers

1. Reference buffer (1x): 10 mM HEPES pH 7.0, 50 mM NaCl, 2 mM MgCl₂, 20 °C (see **Note 1**)

Prepare the desired volume by dissolving the components in H₂O. Adjust the pH using concentrated sodium hydroxide solution. The pH should be set at 20 °C. Fill up to the final volume with H₂O after the pH is adjusted.

2. Deuteration buffer (1x): 10 mM HEPES pD 7.0, 50 mM NaCl, 2 mM MgCl₂, 20 °C (see **Note 2**).

The preparation is similar to the reference buffer, but the components are dissolved in D₂O. Adjusting to pD 7.0 can be done with a standard glass electrode. The pD can be approximated using the following equation (**10**):

$$pD = pH \text{ reading} + 0.41 \text{ (eq 1)}$$

Adjust the buffer pD with concentrated sodium hydroxide dissolved in D₂O (see **Note 3**).

3. Quench buffer (1x): 200 mM ammonium formate (NH₄HCO₂) pH 2.6, 1.5 M urea (see **Note 4**),

0 °C. For 250 mL, dissolve 3.18 g ammonium formate and 22.52 g urea in 200 mL H₂O and cool to 0 °C in an ice-water bath. Use formic acid to adjust the pH. After adjusting the pH, fill up to the final volume.

The solution can be divided into aliquots and stored at -20°C until use.

4. Mobile phase A: 0.6 % (v/v) formic acid in H₂O
5. Mobile phase B: 0.6 % (v/v) formic acid in acetonitrile
6. Mobile phase C: 0.1 % (v/v) formic acid, 1 % methanol in H₂O

7. Pepsin column storage solution: 0.1 % (v/v) formic acid in H₂O
8. Pepsin column washing solution: 1.5 M guanidine hydrochloride, 4 % (v/v) acetonitrile, 0.8 % (v/v) formic acid

2.2 Equipment

The following equipment is used for the experiments in our laboratory, but alternative suppliers are available for all items.

1. Shimadzu Nexera HPLC (modified for HPLC separations to be run at 0.5 °C – see 2.2.1)
2. Laboratory refrigerator unit with glass door and flexible shelves; suitable for enclosing the HPLC system and solvents
3. Bruker impact II QTOF mass spectrometer
4. Pepsin column: Waters® Enzymate™ BEH (2.1 mm x 30 mm)
5. Analytical column: Shim-pack Arata Peptide C18 2.2 μm (2.0 mm x 50 mm)
6. Trap column: Shim-pack GISS-HP(G) C18 (2.1 mm x 10 mm)
7. Thorlabs mounted LEDs (eg. M660L4 - 660 nm, M810L5 - 810 nm, M780L3 - 780 nm)
8. Thorlabs LEDD1B - T-Cube LED Driver
9. Thorlabs SM2F32-A -- Adjustable Collimation Adapter, 350 -- 700 nm
10. Thorlabs SM2P50-B -- Adjustable Collimation Adapter, 650 -- 1050 nm
11. Thermal Incubator for Eppendorf tubes (VWR Thermal Shake Lite or equivalent)
12. Open vessel for liquid nitrogen use -- ideally a 3 L open nitrogen dewar
13. 100 μL gas-tight Hamilton syringe for injections

2.2.1 HDX-MS setup

Commercial HDX-MS setups can be acquired from Waters, ThermoFisher Scientific, and other vendors. In combination with robotic systems these offer automated sample preparation and

injection. However, HDX-MS experiments can also be performed effectively with home-built systems and manual injections, as described below and schematically visualized in Figure 1.

In our HDX-MS setup, we integrated Shimadzu Nexera HPLC pumps (one LC-40B XR binary gradient pump and one LC-20AD single solvent delivery pump), the DGU-405 solvent degassing unit, and the CTO-40C column oven into a laboratory refrigerator unit. The CTO-40C is equipped with a Rheodyne manual injection port for injecting the individual HDX timepoints. All of these parts communicate with a CBM-20A system controller on the outside of the refrigerator, which also allows for the integration of the HPLC into the Bruker Hystar software and communication between the two systems using the Agilent Instrument Control Framework (ICF) plugin.

The refrigerator unit is set to 10 °C, and the CTO-40C column oven is recalibrated to allow for temperature control at 0.5 °C. This is important to reduce the back-exchange from deuterons to protons during the HPLC workup routine of the HDX reactions. All chromatographic steps (sample injection, desalting, and separation of peptides) occur at this low temperature. The only exception is the digestion of the protein samples on the pepsin column. It is positioned outside of the column oven to allow for more efficient pepsin cleavage at 10 °C (see Fig. 1).

The final step of eluting the peptides from the analytical column into the mass spectrometer is enabled by a direct connection of PEEK tubing (red colour, id 0.005") from the column exit port to the ESI-source of the mass spectrometer.

2.3 Software

Bruker HyStar and Agilent ICF plugin for integration of the Shimadzu HPLC system

Bruker oTof control

Bruker DataAnalysis or CompassXport for mzXML export

Hexicon 2 for HDX-MS data analysis **(11)**

3 Methods

In order to efficiently perform the key HDX-MS experiment, some preparatory steps are required.

Therefore, the methods section is divided into specific subsections that allow the reader to address the individual points separately. Each section contains a short justification for why these tasks are important to be carried out and what to consider in the application for other systems to be analysed. Some aspects are also connected between sub-chapters, however, for better readability we have separated them into individual chapters; for example, MS/MS identification, HDX-reactions and HPLC gradient details all refer to specific aspect of the respective other chapters.

3.1 Characterization of Pr and Pfr states using UV/Vis-spectroscopy

A spectroscopic characterization should be performed prior to the HDX experiments to verify that the protein samples are in defined dark- or light-state and also stable for the duration of the deuterium exchange reaction. In addition, the illumination time necessary to reach the PSS must be determined (see **Note 5**). The characterization does not need to be performed in deuteration buffer, but an equivalent aqueous composition should be used. All measurements need to be performed at the same temperature as the HDX reactions, in our case, at 20 °C (see **Note 6**). Make sure to work under safe light conditions that are appropriate for your system of interest; in our case, indirect dim green light can be used to allow for efficient sample handling without actinic light partially activating, and thus negatively affecting, the samples.

1. Dilute the protein stock solution to 5 μM in reference buffer and transfer it to a quartz cuvette. Record an initial spectrum and check the 750 nm absorbance (Pfr indicator). If substantial amounts of protein are in the Pfr state, illuminate with far-red light (780 or 810 nm LED) to fully populate the Pr state.

2. Using a 660 nm LED (see **Note 7**), determine the time needed to fully populate the photostationary state. Initially, illuminate the sample for 15 seconds (irradiance: 2 mW cm⁻²) and record a spectrum.
3. Repeat step 2 until no further spectral changes can be observed (see **Note 8**).
4. Once the PSS is obtained, the protein's stability under constant illumination must be tested. Therefore, the maximally required illumination time (in our case, typically, a 1-hour incubation is the last time point in the deuterium exchange experiment) is simulated. Record a spectrum after 1 hour (see **Note 9**) of constant illumination and check for spectral changes (**Figure 2**) (see **Note 10**).

3.2 Peptide coverage optimization

A key aspect of the method is to identify enough peptide fragments to cover the entire protein sequence. To address the changes in conformational dynamics in a particular region, it is necessary to generate enough peptides during the pepsin digestion step. Since the protein's deuteration does not influence the digestion, it is possible to perform test injections with protein in reference buffer, to identify the ideal amount of protein to be used and/or the optimal contact time between the pepsin column and the sample. Another possibility to influence the coverage is the addition of urea to the quench buffer (see **Note 4**). It will assist protein denaturation and can help to increase coverage for individual structural elements or domains.

1. Prepare 30 µl of protein solution with a concentration of 10 µM in reference buffer.
2. For each test injection, mix 5 µl of protein solution with 45 µl ice-cold quench buffer.
3. Inject 10, 30, or 50 µl of the mixture into your HPLC system (this will yield 10, 30, and 50 pmol of protein per injection). Details of HPLC parameters are provided in chapter 3.7.
4. Follow the chromatograms to observe and compare signal strength. If low amounts of protein injections yield comparable results, this is preferable for the full experiment.

5. Analyze the peptide coverage using the automated data processing software Hexicon 2. Compare the *mzxml* file of the desired injection amount (for example 30 pmol of protein) against itself by importing it twice and arbitrarily assigning a fictional timepoint and the replicate group 1 (see chapter 3.9) in one case. This will provide a *yaml* file that allows the visualization of peptide map plots showing the coverage of peptides across the whole protein (more details are provided in chapter 3.9).
6. Depending on the outcome, either increase the contact time by lowering the flowrate of the HPLC-system during the initial loading phase, or reduce the contact time by increasing the flow rate (see **Note 11**).
7. If the changes in contact time do not allow full coverage of all protein domains, optimize the quench buffer by including chaotropic agents, for example urea.

3.3 MS/MS identification

Once you have identified suitable quench and pepsin digestion conditions to obtain good coverage of the whole protein, at least a substantial fraction of the analysed peptides should be confirmed by MS/MS sequencing. Due to the low specificity of pepsin, many overlapping peptides are generated, and a mass-only-based peptide assignment, as performed by Hexicon 2 and most other HDX analysis packages, runs the risk of wrong assignments and, hence, also interpreting false positives.

Redundancy in similar peptides covering the same region and MS/MS identification help to counteract this potential issue.

1. Quench and digest an aliquot of your protein using the optimized parameters identified in 3.2. The amount used for the MS/MS identification should also be comparable to the standard HDX reactions in order to obtain the same pepsin fragmentation pattern.
2. Inject your sample into the HPLC system and perform a gradient similar to what is described in chapter 3.6. To improve MS/MS identification, however, the gradient should be extended from 4-

5 minutes to 20 minutes. This provides more time for MS/MS fragmentation spectra to be acquired and eventually increases the coverage of MS/MS identified peptides.

3. Use standard MS/MS settings for your mass spectrometer; the AutoMS option in Bruker *oTofControl* is well suited for identification of precursor ions and intensity-based fragmentation.
4. Open the file in *DataAnalysis* and export the fragment spectra as *mgf* file for uploading as an MS/MS ion search in Mascot (**12**).
5. Copy/paste the *peptide summary result* of the top hit into a text file and save for subsequent inclusion in *Hexcion 2* runs (see 3.8). Adjust the file structure according to the software's readme file, if needed (see **Note 12**).

3.4 HDX sample preparation

The amount of protein needed for the experiment depends on the analysed protein, but roughly 30 pmol per injection should give a strong signal. This is determined by the test injections described in chapter 3.2. The following instructions correspond to 30 pmol protein per injection as used in the *DrBphP* experiments.

1. Prepare at least five 2 μ l aliquots of 175 μ M protein in Eppendorf tubes for each functional state to be analysed (i.e., *DrBphP* measurements under dark and light conditions require at least 10 aliquots) – per functional state we typically prepare: 1 aliquot for each replicate (triplicates at least), one for the undeuterated reference, and one backup sample (see **Note 13**). Use your standard storage buffer to dilute the samples. If the initial spectroscopic characterization has revealed mixed Pr/Pfr states (see 3.1), use appropriate LEDs (780 or 810 nm) to fully populate a defined state and carefully handle the sample under indirect dim green light conditions.
2. Ensure the protein solution is placed at the bottom of the tubes.
3. Freeze the tubes in liquid nitrogen and store them at -80°C until you perform the reactions.

3.5 HDX reactions

Automated systems for timing deuteration reactions exist. However, we report an experimental approach without such automated robotic systems. Therefore, the individual samples must be injected manually. Once enough reaction timepoints have been collected, the injections can be done in parallel to the incubation of reactions. Keep in mind that the safe-light conditions have to be maintained for the dark-adapted samples throughout the reaction. Dark-adapted and photostationary state reactions differ during the initial equilibration step. For the latter, illuminate the sample during the initial thermal equilibration, while safe-light conditions need to be maintained during the equilibration of dark-adapted samples. Adjust the length of this step according to the time needed to reach the PSS (based on the results from the characterization described under 3.1). In our case, we use 2 min as defined in chapter 3.1 and Figure 2.

1. Thaw a 2 μl aliquot and equilibrate in a thermoblock set to 20°C for 2 min, under safe-light settings for dark-state measurements or with parallel red-light illumination for light-state experiments. The distance of the LED to the sample is set to 15 cm to allow for efficient handling of the sample.
2. Add 38 μl deuteration buffer and ensure homogenous mixing.
3. After ~8 seconds, withdraw 4 μl of the reaction and mix 1+1 with ice-cold quench buffer (see **Note 14**) once the timer reaches 10 seconds by pipetting up and down 3-4 times (see **Note 15**). Immediately freeze the sample in liquid nitrogen to minimize back exchange. This will be your first timepoint.
4. Similarly, take samples for 45, 180, 900, and 3,600 second timepoints to complete one time series. Close the lid of the Eppendorf tube between taking samples after the 45 s timepoint to minimize condensation effects.
5. Repeat this workflow, starting at point 1, twice to obtain experimental triplicates (see **Note 16**).

6. Before injecting each sample into the HPLC, thaw the aliquot by pipetting 50 μ l ice-cold quench buffer onto the frozen pellets. Pipet up and down until the pellet is thawed completely (see **Note 17**).
7. Use an ice-cold Hamilton syringe to withdraw 50 μ l sample and inject it into the HPLC port.
8. Follow the chromatograms of individual injections to observe obvious outliers. At this stage, additional replicates can be performed if needed using the excess protein aliquots available. Make sure to have three usable measurements for each time point to allow for subsequent statistical analysis.

3.6 Reference sample preparation

Prepare an undeuterated reference sample by performing an equivalent dilution to chapter 3.5 for a protein aliquot with reference buffer. No specific incubation time is needed; therefore, directly dilute your sample with quench buffer and inject into the HPLC system.

3.7 HPLC gradient details

The following description outlines the most important settings for the separation method used in our setup. The times and flow rates for the steps mentioned are influenced by the volume of the connecting PEEK or metal tubing. Additional steps like washing the flow path and the trap column are necessary to reduce carry-over and might need to be adjusted for each individual setup.

1. Set the flow rate of the isocratic pump carrying mobile phase C to 0.3 mL/min to flush the injection loop containing the sample and to bring the latter in contact with the pepsin column for online digestion. By changing the flow rate during this initial step, you can influence the contact time between the sample and the column (see **Note 11**). The cleavage efficiency of pepsin is not only affected by the contact time but also by pressure. Therefore, the relationship between efficiency and contact time is not always linear.

2. After 1.5 min, increase the flow rate to 0.5 mL/min. This completes the loading of the sample onto the trap column (before switching to the higher flow rate, the whole sample should have passed the pepsin column) and eventually also allows washing off any undesired compounds.
3. Terminate the loading and washing phase of the trap column by switching to the corresponding valve setting (Figure 1) after 3 min. This initiates the elution phase by putting the trap column in line with the binary pump and the analytical column. Set the binary pump to deliver mobile phases A and B; during the elution phase, a gradient from 10% to 45% mobile phase B is run over a period of 4.5 min. The analytical column is used to improve separation of the peptides before entering the ESI-MS (see **Note 18**).
4. Wash the column during each individual injection using a short gradient from 45% to 95% of mobile phase B as part of the HPLC programme.
5. Finally, equilibrate the trap and analytical columns to 10% B to prepare them for the next sample.
6. Test for carry-over between individual injections by running a blank injection (quench buffer only) after the first samples. If you observe less than 10 % carry-over (see **Note 19**), you can proceed with your different timepoint injections. It is good laboratory practice to randomize individual injections rather than following the order of time points taken, to prevent systematic effects influencing your outcome.
7. Once you have finished all injections make sure to store your pepsin column in the appropriate storage solution and your chromatographic equipment according to your standard operating procedures.

3.8 Parameters of the mass spectrometer

The settings on the mass spectrometer depend a lot on your specific system and the HPLC flow-rates employed. Recommendations on how to set critical MS parameters for Bruker electrospray hybrid

quadrupole, time-of-flight devices like the impact II (as used in our specific case) or maXis are provided below.

1. For data acquisition control, use positive ion mode and calibrate the device for a mass range from 500 m/z to 3000 m/z with a repetition rate of two spectra per second. To reduce the amount of data to be analysed subsequently, use a threshold of 45 counts per 1000 summations (see **Note 20**).
2. Considering the HPLC flow rate of 0.3 mL/min, adjust the nebulizer and dry gas settings to 2.6 bar and 11 L/min, respectively. The dry gas temperature should be set to 200 °C. Adjust as needed if signal strength drops significantly and/or liquid droplets accumulate in the source.
3. All other settings can remain at their standard values, optimized for the current state of your funnel and collision cell, the detector lifetime, etc.

3.9 HDX Data analysis

For HDX-MS data analysis, a range of software packages have been developed over the years (**13**).

Below we describe the typical workflow for the software package Hexicon 2 (**11**), which provides a straight-forward workflow and a flexible and easy to use interface for data analysis and visualization.

1. The data from each HDX timepoint and the reference need be exported as line spectra in *mzXML* format. Depending on your data analysis software, this can either be done directly or by using applications like CompassXport (Bruker).
2. Open Hexicon 2 and import the data files of one functional state (dark or light) individually or all at once. In the single file import scenario, you are prompted to define the respective timepoint of each measurement and assign a replicate group upon importing. The standard convention for the replicate groups is: 0 -- reference; 1 -- first timepoint; 2 -- second timepoint; and so on. In case of importing all *mzxml* files at once, the timepoints and replicate groups need to be defined in the respective boxes of the dataset window after successfully loading the files.

3. Load the text-based *Mascot* file for the respective Mascot search report (see chapter 3.3) in the corresponding line. Follow the guidelines in the Hexicon 2 readme file to have the correct file architecture.
4. Load the text-based protein sequence file in the next line. Make sure you have an amino acid only sequence file corresponding exactly to the protein used in the experiment. Any purification tags or cloning artefacts should be included to allow the software to look for the respective peptide sequences. Covalent protein modifications with cofactors (such as biliverdin in the case of phytochromes) or phosphorylation can also be defined, if needed (see **Note 21**).
5. You can optionally provide a reference protein sequence file that contains only the corresponding database entry for your protein of interest. Thereby all residues are labelled with their numbers as used in reference publications.
6. Save the data import contents for quick loading of the corresponding data for subsequent Hexicon 2 runs with potentially altered and optimised run settings (see point 8 below).
7. The next tab, *Filters*, allows you to specify proteins of a mixture that should be ignored; for example, in the case of analysing protein complexes. This is not needed in the specific case of a single protein analysis.
8. On the next tab, *Parameters*, the above-mentioned settings of each run need to be specified. Adjust the retention time window according to the time frame where peptides are analysed in the mass spectrometer. Based on our dead volumes and connector lengths, this is between 140 and 480 seconds, typically. Also, specify a resolution that reflects the current analyses -- we use 40,000. The calibration error should be specified in a realistic window, even though Hexicon 2 performs an internal re-calibration -- 10 ppm should be on the safe side. The noise quantile setting depends on your stringency of filtering noise using the threshold option in the data acquisition step. Typically, 0.05 should be good, but this might need optimization in both directions.

9. Last but not least, you need to specify an export path where your data are stored, and you can optimize the advanced settings, if needed. Typically, lower values result in more peptides being identified, but potentially also more noise and wrong assignments being exported.
10. Start the Hexicon 2 run on the next tab and let the workflow proceed until the end. This generates a *yaml* file that can then be opened in the HXViewer executable of the Hexicon 2 package.
11. Repeat this procedure from step 2 onwards for each functional state of interest and save as a separate *yaml* file -- from our analysis, we eventually get *DrBphP_dark.yaml* and *DrBphP_light.yaml*.

3.10 HDX data interpretation and reporting

The most interesting aspect of performing HDX measurements is their interpretation and the way you use it to enrich your functional analyses of your protein of interest. A comprehensive description of how to interpret HDX data, however, goes beyond this method chapter, and the reader is referred to review articles, for example (7). Here, we provide a few example figures that Hexicon 2 can generate based on the two *yaml* files created in the first part of the analysis workflow (chapter 3.8).

1. Open both *yaml* files in the HXViewer application of Hexicon 2 and give them meaningful names, as these will be shown in the analyses.
2. Process both data files to reduce the number of sequence conflicts using Hexicon 2's inbuilt feature based on pepsin cleavage probabilities -- "*Processing -- Resolve sequence conflicts*".
3. Double-click on a peptide and assign a colour for this peptide series. We use black for the dark state peptides. This opens a window with the deuterium incorporation over time for this respective peptide. Activate the software-estimated distribution of deuterated species by clicking on the histogram button at the bottom of the plot. Filter outlier peptides (potential wrong-assignments, overlapping intensities from other signals, noisy signals, ...) by going through

- all peptides and checking for smooth deuteration distributions as well as physically meaningful deuterium incorporation kinetics. Right-click outliers to inactivate them and remove them from reporting. Repeat this for the second functional state -- we use red for *DrBphP_light* peptides.
4. To visualize the intrinsic conformational dynamics of the protein, go to “*Visualization -- Peptide map*” and select, for example, the dark dataset as reference. No target is required in this case.
 5. In the newly opened window, set the dynamic range to 0.75 to account for a maximum incorporation of 70-75 % deuterium under the assumption of 25-30 % back-exchange during the work-up routine.
 6. Open a *dssp* description file (according to the Hexicon 2 instructions) by clicking on the black arrow at the bottom right. This allows us to visualize secondary structure elements in addition to the primary sequence in these so-called deuteration plots. An example for the dark-state of *DrBphP* is shown in Figure 3. This reveals regions in blue with low relative deuterium incorporation -- i.e., stable core regions of structured domains -- versus orange or red colours for regions with substantial incorporation of deuterium due to increased conformational dynamics or being unstructured.
 7. To visualize only regions affected by the perturbation between two functional states, i.e., *DrBphP_light* relative to *DrBphP_dark*, again select “*Visualization -- Peptide map*”, but use the *DrBphP_light yamI* file as target dataset in this case.
 8. In the newly opened window, set the dynamic range according to the amplitude of changes seen between the two states. For *DrBphP*, 2.8 is a good setting when using 7 colours (to be set at the right bottom of the plot) for visualizing effects of illumination in interesting regions and obtaining simple numbers for individual bin descriptions in the colour-bar legend, but this can be adjusted according to your needs. Figure 4 shows such a comparison plot where red regions indicate elements with increased deuterium uptake in the light-activated state, and blue regions correspond to a stabilization of the respective element due to red light irradiation.

9. Right-clicking on regions of interest and selecting “*Show time series*” permits visualization of the respective peptides’ deuterium incorporation plots of dark and light datasets side-by-side. Use black for dark-state data and red for the respective light-state peptides, and scroll through the list of peptides. Interesting peptides can then be analysed in more detail and exported for publications. An example of four interesting regions is shown in Figure 5.
10. All relevant plots can be exported as line-art pdf and can then be imported into your favourite illustration application to prepare publication quality figures.
11. Last, but not least, prepare a summary table that reports on the key parameters and the statistical analysis of your HDX-experiments as described in Masson et al. (7). An example table for the analyses described in this chapter is provided below (Table 1). A python-based script to facilitate the extraction and comparison process between two datasets (based on two Hexicon 2 *yaml* files) can be made available upon request.

4 Notes

- 1 Use the optimal buffer system for your system of interest. HDX-MS is also compatible with complex buffer mixtures. Just ensure you keep it as simple as possible, not to make the experiments unnecessarily expensive due to the need for more complex deuterated chemicals to prepare the deuteration buffer. If you have to include substantial amounts of additives, for example glycerol, make sure to include the corresponding deuterated compound with all exchangeable hydrogens replaced by deuterium; in the latter case, glycer(ol-d3) would be needed.
- 2 Prepare more buffer than you need for one experiment. Excess buffer can be frozen and stored for later use, increasing reproducibility and comparability between experiments also over longer intervals.
- 3 In order to prevent overshooting the pD value, you can estimate the amounts of acid/base needed by preparing an equivalent amount of aqueous buffer initially and quantifying the amounts used to obtain the desired values.
- 4 The urea included in the quench buffer is optional and depends on the protein of interest. Initial testing for peptide coverage should be performed without including urea. Only if inefficient digestion of individual parts of the protein is observed and variation of contact times with the pepsin column (see **Note 11**) also does not improve the situation, should increasing concentrations of urea be tested. Apart from urea, other chaotropic substances like guanidine-HCl can also be used. Double check the manual of your specific pepsin column to check which concentrations of chaotropic agents are tolerated. Reducing agents can also be added to the quench buffer to handle disulfide bridges, if present.
- 5 The illumination setup should resemble the setup you use during the HDX experiments. This refers to the distance between the sample and the LED source, light intensity and protein concentration.

- 6 The temperature of the experiment is an additional variable that can be used to enhance the understanding of your system. Lower temperatures result in slower deuterium exchange and can, therefore, be interesting for areas that show particularly fast deuterium exchange. In contrast, higher temperatures might be interesting for areas that show medium-slow exchange with only moderate uptake of deuterium and consequently only subtle observable effects of your perturbation of interest at standard temperatures.
- 7 Use the LED, which gives the highest contribution of Pfr in the photostationary state.
- 8 Depending on the protein of interest, the required red light activation times to obtain a steady-state of forward (Pr to Pfr) and backward (Pfr to Pr) rates (the photostationary state - PSS) can vary substantially between seconds to minutes.
- 9 The longest timepoint of the experiment is determined by the dynamics of the system and the features one is interested in. For photoreceptors with relatively high intrinsic conformational dynamics, 1 hour is typically enough to see the elements affected by illumination.
- 10 For red light illumination, we have not observed any negative effects of 1 hour illumination at an irradiance of 2 mW cm^{-2} so far. Depending on the wavelength of the employed LED and the irradiance required to effectively populate the light-activated state, this should, however, be confirmed for each experimental system. In case of observable bleaching or other unexpected spectral changes, the irradiance should be lowered until a constant spectrum is observed during the duration of the experiment. In that case, the time needed to reach the photostationary state might also need readjustment. If your system of interest has a very slow thermal relaxation to the dark state, one could also omit the constant illumination during the deuterium exchange reaction; in this scenario, the stability control experiment could be omitted, but might still be valuable to check for aggregation or other effects of long incubations.

- 11 The contact time between protein and pepsin column defines the cleavage pattern and influences the observed sequence coverage. Too long contact times can result in many short peptides, which are sometimes less informative than longer ones, because the first two amide hydrogens are quickly back-exchanged to hydrogen during the work-up of the HDX reactions. Therefore, aim for an average peptide length of 10-15 amino acids. Too short contact times, on the other hand, may reduce the coverage by incomplete digestion of the protein; this can be seen by very long peptides eluting towards the end of the HPLC gradient.
- 12 You can also combine multiple MS/MS identification runs into one joint *massot* file for Hexicon 2. Just make sure to remove redundant entries and to have unique identifiers for each peptide. To improve the coverage, you can put already identified peptides into an exclusion list and/or specifically extract m/z values from Hexicon 2 to be included in an inclusion list for your MS/MS measurements.
- 13 The number of aliquots you prepare will depend on the number of measurements you want to perform. Generally, you should do triplicate measurements for both Pr (dark) and photostationary state (light). However, we recommend preparing additional aliquots in case of a user error. This ensures that you have the same stock for all measurements.
- 14 Prepare 0.5 mL Eppendorf tubes with 4 μ l of quench buffer beforehand and put them on ice. Label the tubes according to timepoint.
- 15 To make the process more efficient, it is recommended to perform the reactions for the triplicates in parallel, with slightly different starting times. The handling, especially of short timepoints, should initially be practiced using water and dummy aliquots to optimize the procedure. To reduce the amount of handling in the initial steps, the timer is started at the equilibration stage. In case of two minutes equilibration, just let the timer continue to run and mix sample with deuteration buffer at the 2:00 reading. Quenching auf the first timepoint is then performed at a reading of 2:10.

- 16 A foam rack in the liquid nitrogen dewar can help you track your reactions/injections. If no suitable design is at hand, you can easily make one yourself using any styrofoam lid.
- 17 The thawing process should be performed as consistently as possible. Consistently wipe down the condensate from the tube to have a clear view of the samples. Do not constantly heat up the sample in your fingers during the process, as this will negatively affect the back-exchange and result in excessive loss of your deuterium signal.
- 18 The length of the analytical column is a compromise between efficient separation of peptides and short runtimes. In our hands, a 5 cm column allows for sufficiently well-separated peptides at the average resolution of 40,000 - 50,000 of our impact II mass spectrometer in a relatively short gradient of 4-5 minutes.
- 19 Substantial carry-over is an issue because the sample peptides continue to lose their incorporated deuterium (back-exchange). Thereby carry-over of signal from one injection to the next falsifies your extracted isotope distribution. Reasons for carry-over can be manifold and sometimes difficult to identify. In case you observe carry-over, watch out for precipitation of your sample upon quenching (trapping on inline filters and slow continuous release of protein), efficient washing of the flow-path, injection port and columns between injections. If you observe carry-over, also more intense cleaning of the pepsin column might be indicated. Use the pepsin column washing solution offline or manually inject 100 μ L of it between individual runs.
- 20 Depending on your choice of sample amounts loaded and background signals in your mass spectrometer system, we recommend to vary the threshold parameter to eventually end up with line spectra *mzxml* files that have ~30-100 Mb per run.
- 21 Hexicon 2 offers a versatile modification option, where the user can define any chemical modification, provided the chemistry of the linkage and the added compound is known. Follow the guidelines in Hexicon 2 software to modify the modifications file (*modifications.yaml*) as needed.

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Figure Legends

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the home-built HDX-MS setup. The differences in the flow path between the load and elute phases of the separation method are highlighted. During the load phase, the isocratic pump transports the sample from the injection loop via the pepsin column to the trap column. Switching to the elution phase connects the binary gradient pump with the trap column and the analytical column. A gradient is used to elute the peptides from the column and transport them towards the mass spectrometer.

Fig. 2. UV/Vis absorption spectrum of DrBphP from *Deinococcus radiodurans*. The shift from dark (Pr) to light state (Pfr, 2 min vs. 1h illumination time) is shown for conditions resembling the experimental setup for the HDX-MS reactions. For better visibility of subtle differences, we show only

a close-up of the Q-band, which is red-shifted upon illumination with a 660 nm LED for the indicated times.

Fig. 3. Deuterium map of *DrBphP* in its dark state. The graph shows the relative deuterium incorporation for each peptide at each labelling timepoint. Individual timepoints of each peptide are coloured from bottom up. Colours correspond to the amount of deuterium incorporated normalized to peptide length. The scale bar settings have been adjusted to account for a back-exchange of ~30%. Regions in blue incorporate fewer deuterons compared to regions in orange and red. White diamond symbols indicate MS/MS identified peptides. The arrow and cylinder symbols below the peptides correspond to the secondary structure according to the cryo-EM structure of *DrBphP* and the numbers reflect the positions of the primary sequence.

Fig. 4. Difference map emphasizing changes in deuterium exchange kinetics between dark and light states. The two functional states of *DrBphP* are compared by subtracting the deuterium incorporation in the light state from that of the corresponding dark state. Blue regions correspond to a stabilization

in the light state, while red regions reflect increased conformational dynamics. The absolute differences are coloured according to the bar legend. Each box corresponds to one peptide with individual colours from bottom to top corresponding to the increasing timepoints. White diamond symbols indicate MS/MS identified peptides. The arrow and cylinder symbols below the peptides correspond to the secondary structure according to the cryo-EM structure of *DrBphP* and the numbers reflect the positions of the primary sequence.

Fig. 5. Selected peptides of the *DrBphP* analysis show-casing different scenarios when comparing two functional states. In all panels, the deuterium incorporation is plotted against time for dark (black lines) and light-state (red lines) measurements. Below these graphs, the Hexicon 2 estimated deuterium level of each peptide is plotted for each timepoint and functional state. Above each graph, the corresponding peptide sequence and position in the protein is shown. **A)** Although both states start with similar deuteration levels, the light state incorporates more deuterons over time, which shows that illumination leads to increased conformational dynamics in an otherwise well-ordered region. This peptide shows up in red for the later timepoints in Fig. 4. **B)** A well-structured region with

low conformational dynamics and hence slow deuterium incorporation in both dark and light state – representative for grey peptides in Fig. 4. **C)** A peptide with drastic increase in conformational dynamics for the light state, corresponding to a structural change from very rigid to almost unstructured. Dark red peptide in Figure 4. **D)** Increased deuterium incorporation in the light state over the course of the time series. The light state also shows a bimodal deuterium incorporation distribution, which likely corresponds to a mixed population with an altered conformation of a part of the peptide that features rapid exchange kinetics. Also a red peptide in Fig. 4, but different functional interpretation compared to panels a and c.

Table Legend

Table 1. Detailed overview of the acquired HDX datasets and their comparison.

	<i>DrBphP</i>	
Light conditions	Dark	Light (660 nm)
HDX reaction details	10 mM HEPES, 50 mM NaCl, 2 mM MgCl ₂ , pD = 7.0, 20 °C	
HDX time course (s)	10, 45, 180, 900, 3600	
HDX control samples	Unlabeled control	
Back-exchange	Not measured	
# of Peptides	234	226
Sequence coverage	96%	96%
Avg. peptide length/ Average Redundancy	14 / 4.2	14 / 4.0
Replicates	3	3
Repeatability (average SD for each time point)	0.05, 0.06, 0.09, 0.05, 0.13	0.06, 0.07, 0.10, 0.08, 0.09
Sign. Diff. in HDX	$\Delta\text{HDX} > 0.3 \text{ D}$	